

The Influence of Logistics Information System on Customer Satisfaction

Nguyen Thi Mai Anh^{1}, Dao Quynh Chi¹, Nguyen Thi Ngoc Binh¹, Pham Thi Thi¹,
Nguyen Thi Hong Ngoc¹*

(¹). Faculty of Business Administration, Hanoi university of Industry

** Corresponding author: anhntm@hau.edu.vn*

Abstract:

This article aims to examine the impact of the Logistics information system on customer satisfaction. Quantitative analysis is based on data taken from a survey of individuals and businesses operating in Vietnam that have used Logistics information systems. Research results show that the groups of factors that constitute the quality of Logistics information systems such as usefulness, reliability, ease of use and flexibility have an impact on customer satisfaction. These research results have important implications for the practice of Logistics information systems of businesses, and can serve as a basis for proposing solutions to perfect and improve the quality of Logistics information systems to the level of customer satisfaction when using.

Keywords: Logistics information system, satisfaction, information system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The international landscape has recently witnessed significant fluctuations across various economic, social, and political fronts, impacting the overall global economic development and the growth of individual economies. Governments and businesses are making continuous efforts to regain momentum in the logistics sector, emphasizing its pivotal role and positioning it as a key driver for the economy. The breakthroughs of the Fourth Industrial Revolution have provided opportunities for logistics enterprises to optimize processes, enhance efficiency, and reduce costs. In this process, logistics information systems have emerged as an indispensable core element. They play a crucial role in providing accurate information, managing data effectively, and optimizing

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transportation and storage processes. Logistics information systems serve as vital bridges, ensuring that information related to the status of goods, transportation, and delivery is provided to customers fully, accurately, and promptly. Currently, there have been numerous notable domestic and international studies, such as:

The study by Agyapong-Mensah, Ahenkorah et al. (2019) on "The Impact of Logistics Information Technology on Organizational Performance: The Mediating Role of Supply Chain Integration and Customer Satisfaction", the research conducted by Chang, YongFei et al. (2019) on "The Impact of Logistics Information Services on Customer Satisfaction: An Experimental Study with Assurance as a Moderator", and the study by Kalkan (2018) on "The Relationship between the Use of Information Technology in Logistics Companies, Customer Satisfaction, and Business Performance" are significant contributions in the field.

The study by Hung (2020) on "The Impact of Information Systems on the Competitive Advantage of Import-Export Freight Forwarding Companies and Customs Brokerage Agents in Ho Chi Minh City" and the work presented by Hòa (2023) on "The Application of Information Technology in Logistics Enterprises: Analyzing the Current Situation of Information Technology Application in Vietnamese Logistics Enterprises" are valuable contributions to understanding the role of information technology in the logistics industry, particularly within the context of Vietnam.

In general, there are some gaps identified in both domestic and international scientific research. Firstly, studies mainly focus on understanding the quality of logistics information systems without delving into the relationship between the quality of these systems and customer satisfaction. Secondly, research tends to be qualitative or descriptive in nature, with limited quantitative studies conducted to determine the extent of influence of various factors contributing to the quality of logistics information systems and customer satisfaction. Recognizing these research gaps, our research team conducted a study on the factors constituting the quality of logistics information systems and focused on the relationship between the quality of these systems and customer satisfaction to provide a more comprehensive insight into the theory and practice in this field.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Logistics information system

According to Ballou (1993), a Logistics Information System is a subsystem of the overall Management Information System that provides specific information for logistics management. Lambert, Stock et al. (1998) describe this system as a computer-based information system supporting all aspects of comprehensive logistics management, including coordinating and managing various activities such as planning, inventory replenishment, flow scheduling, etc.

2.2. Quality of Logistics Information system

The authors and research cited from Gorla, Somers et al. (2010) and Seddon, Staples et al. (1999) suggest that the quality of information systems is measured by the extent to which the system meets the requirements, needs, and expectations of users. There are numerous metrics for assessing the quality of information systems, such as in the study by Al-Debei, Jalal et al. (2013), where system quality is measured by attributes such as ease of use, functionality, reliability, data quality, flexibility, and integration. After reviewing these studies, the author team decided to focus on four groups of factors reflecting the quality of logistics information systems that are deemed most important to customers: usefulness, reliability, ease of use, and flexibility.

Usefulness

According to Davis (1989), the usefulness of an information system refers to its ability to improve the performance of users. This implies that the system can support users' tasks, as discussed by Kumar (1990) and Ramon Gil-Garcia, Chengalur-Smith et al. (2007). Lim and Benbasat (2000) argue that users only perceive a system as useful if it helps them perform tasks for which it was designed.

Reliability

The reliability of a logistics information system is a decisive factor in the competitiveness of businesses (Gajewska and Zimon 2018). Reliability is not only about the ability to provide accurate information about the status of orders but also includes the

ability to meet predetermined deadlines and timely notification to customers in case of delivery failure (Rife, Khanafseh et al. 2008).

Ease of use

The extent to which an individual believes that using technology will make it easier for them to accomplish their tasks is referred to as perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989). Metrics such as ease of learning, ease of control, ease of understanding, flexibility, ease of application, and usability are used to assess this factor. According to Ramayah and Ignatius (2005), ease of use is also described through aspects such as ease of system or technology usage; clarity and understandability; simplicity; overall ease of use.

Flexibility

Flexibility is the ability to change or respond with minimal loss of time, effort, cost, or performance (Upton, 1994). This includes the system's ability to adapt to various users' needs and changing conditions (Nelson and Bandy, 2005). The flexibility of an information system involves handling special situations within organizational functions or industry needs (Palanisamy, 2003), adapting to changes in regulations or other environments (Bruns Jr and McFarlan, 1987), and meeting specific customer requirements.

2.3. Customer satisfaction

Many researchers argue that satisfaction is the difference between customer expectations and the actual perceived experience. According to Johnson, Anderson et al. (1995) and Hansemark and Albinsson (2004), satisfaction or dissatisfaction is the overall attitude or response of customers associated with feelings of acceptance, happiness, assistance, excitement, and joy (Mohsan, Nawaz et al., 2011) regarding the difference between pre-consumption expectations and post-consumption perceptions of the product.

3. THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT

3.1. The relationship between usefulness and customer satisfaction.

The usefulness of the information system is not only an important factor but also one of the key elements to ensure user satisfaction. Useful is defined by the system's ability to provide accurate and timely information, enabling users to perform their tasks efficiently

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(Zviran, Pliskin et al., 2005; Ayyash, 2015). A useful information system not only benefits the organization but also generates customer satisfaction by providing accurate information and effective support services. Providing customer support services based on accurate information can improve customer satisfaction through closer interaction with customers (Rossler and Hirsz, 1996).

Based on these arguments, the author proposes the following hypothesis:

“H1: The usefulness of logistics information system has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.”

3.2. The relationship of reliability and customer satisfaction

Based on the highlighted research findings, the relationship between the reliability of the logistics information system and customer satisfaction emerges as a prominent point. Gardiner, Aasheim et al. (2018) have demonstrated that the system's reliability is closely related to customer satisfaction, based on a survey conducted among a sample of customers. When the logistics information system is reliable and provides accurate and timely information, customers tend to feel more satisfied with the business's services. Li, Qiu et al. (2017) have also substantiated this correlation through data analysis from e-commerce enterprises.

Based on the arguments above, the author proposes the following hypothesis:

“H2: The reliability of logistics information system has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.”

3.3. The relationship between ease of use and customer satisfaction.

In the studies by Urbach and Müller (2012), Seddon (1997), and Petter, DeLone et al. (2008), the quality of the information system is linked to ease of use and factors such as reliability and convenience. Meanwhile, Wang, Tang et al. (2001) emphasize the important aspects of user satisfaction on the web, with ease of use being one of the key factors. Thakur (2019) discusses how a well-designed and user-friendly interface can create a positive impression on customers, contributing to satisfaction. The research by Floh and Treiblmaier (2006) also confirms that usability influences customer satisfaction.

Based on these arguments, the author proposes the following hypothesis:

“H3: The ease of use of the information system has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.”

3.4. The relationship between flexibility and customer satisfaction

Flexibility is not just about enhancing diversity and options for customers but also about the ability to respond quickly and efficiently to changes without causing significant losses in time, effort, or costs (Upton, 1994). Flexibility is the capability of an information system to adapt and adjust to meet the new conditions, needs, or circumstances of the organization. Moreover, flexibility is also demonstrated through personalization and customization of services according to specific customer requests, creating a sense of being cared for and special, thereby enhancing their satisfaction and loyalty (Aladwani and Palvia, 2002).

Based on these arguments, the author proposes the following hypothesis:

“H4: The flexibility of the information system has a positive impact on customer satisfaction.”

3.5. Research model

Fig 1: Research model

Research Hypothesis:

Hypothesis H1: Usefulness positively influences on customer satisfaction

Hypothesis H2: Reliability positively influences on customer satisfaction

Hypothesis H3: Ease of use positively influences customer satisfaction

Hypothesis H4: Flexibility positively influences on customer satisfaction

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4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Measurement model

The items of the questionnaire were obtained from the relevant literature. The details of items and sources are presented in table 1.

Variable Names	Observations (Scale)	Citation Sources
Usefulness	Include 4 observational variables	(Lin 2007); (Nelson 2005); (Wang and Chen 2006, Saeed and Abdinnour-Helm 2008); (McHaney and Cronan 2000); Cockerill et al., 2004
Reliability	Include 3 observational variables	(Aladwani and Palvia 2002) ;(Wang and Chen 2006); (Bailey and Pearson 1983) và (Nelson, Todd et al. 2005)
Ease of use	Include 4 observational variables	(Miller and Doyle 1987, Aladwani and Palvia 2002); (Sedera, Gable et al. 2004); (Jun and Cai 2001)
Flexibility	Include 5 observational variables	Nelson et al. (2005); (Aladwani and Palvia 2002); (DeLone and McLean 2003); (Bailey and Pearson 1983, Sedera, Gable et al. 2004)
Customer satisfaction	Include 5 observational variables	(Chiu, Chiu et al. 2007); (Zhou, Zhao et al. 2020)

Tab 1. Measurement scale and sources

4.2. Data collection method

The data collection method involves secondary data collection through relevant research documents both domestically and internationally to clarify the urgency and establish the theoretical basis of the study. Next, the author group conducted primary data collection through survey questionnaires. The survey subjects are customers who could be individuals or businesses that have used logistics information systems. The survey questionnaire includes 4 independent variables: (1) Flexibility; (2) Reliability; (3) Usability; (4) Adaptability. All observational variables in the components use a 5-point Likert scale with corresponding levels: level 1 - strongly disagree, level 2 - disagree, level 3 - undecided, level 4 - agree, and level 5 - strongly agree. After a period of sending out questionnaires, the group collected 155 questionnaires, of which 5 were invalid. Therefore, 150 valid questionnaires were used and entered into data analysis using SPSS software.

4.3. Data processing method

The collected data was analyzed and processed using SPSS software with the following statistical analyses and tests: Cronbach's Alpha coefficient analysis to eliminate inappropriate variables and limit junk variables during the research process. After analyzing the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient, the scales were further evaluated using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to reduce and merge variables into factors. This involved examining the convergence of observational variables within each component and the discriminant validity between factors. Finally, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the extent of the impact of the logistics information system on customer satisfaction based on the factors: usefulness, reliability, usability, and flexibility.

5. RESEARCH RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1. Research results

5.1.1. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics of the sample are presented in Table 1.

Elements		Frequency (%)
Customer base	Business	36,7
	Individual	63,3
Business field	Agriculture production	18,2

	Industrial production	32,7
	Service	34,5
	Finance – Bank	5,9
	Insurance	4,1
	Education	4,5
Target market	Domestic	61,5
	Overseas	38,5
Practice of Logistics Information System	Used	100
	Have not used yet	0
Logistics information system used	Warehouse information system	26,4
	Transportation information system	22,6
	Delivery information system	26,8
	E-commerce information system	24,2
Time using Logistics Information system	Under 6 months	9,3
	Between 6 months and 1 year	26,0
	Between 1 and 2 years	33,3
	Above 2 years	31,3

Tab 1. Descriptive statistics

5.1.2. Testing the reliability of a scale using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

The results of the analysis indicate that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are all greater than 0.6. The Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficients of the observed variables are all > 0.3 , indicating that the research concepts constructed from the observed variables are acceptable and will be used in the subsequent factor analysis.

5.1.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) for independent variables

KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO		,857
Bartlett's Test	Approximate chi-square.	1302,262
	df	120
	Sig.	,000

Tab 3: The results of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test and Bartlett's test for the independent variable group.

(Source: The results of processing survey data in the SPSS software)

The results of the factor analysis show that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure is 0.857, which is greater than 0.5. This indicates a high degree of model appropriateness.

The Barlett's Test of Sphericity yields a value of 1302.262 with a significance level (p-value) of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the variables are correlated with each other and meet the conditions for factor analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Factor loadings			
	1	2	3	4
LH2	0,858			
LH5	0,814			
LH3	0,814			
LH1	0,803			
LH4	0,798			
SD4		0,895		
SD2		0,825		
SD1		0,809		
SD3		0,805		
HI4			0,838	
HI2			0,814	
HI1			0,808	
HI3			0,798	
TC1				0,821
TC2				0,783

TC3				0,764
Eigenvalue	1,460			
Total variance extracted	72,206			

Tab 4: Factor rotation matrix.

(Source: The results of processing survey data in the SPSS software)

All independent observed variables have factor loadings above 0.6. The results of the factor analysis are consistent with the initial assumptions of the research model.

The total variance extracted is 72.206%, which is greater than the recommended threshold of 50%, indicating that it meets the requirement. The eigenvalues of all factors are high (>1). These results indicate that the observed variables are correlated with each other in the overall dataset, and the exploratory factor analysis is appropriate.

5.1.4. Exploratory Factor Analysis for dependent variables

In the research model, the group of dependent variables consists of 5 observed variables, namely HL1, HL2, HL3, HL4, and HL5.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO		,862
Bartlett's test	Approximate Chi-Square	340,473
	df	10
	Sig.	,000

Tab 5: The results of the KMO (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) test and Bartlett's test for the dependent variable group.

(Source: The results of processing survey data in the SPSS software.)

The results of the analysis (Table 5) show that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy is 0.862, indicating that the analyzed data are very suitable for factor analysis and the factor analysis is appropriate. The assumption of correlation

between the observed variables included in the analysis is accepted with a Sig. value of the Bartlett's test of 0.000, which is less than 0.05.

*Tab 6:
Exploratory
Analysis
results for the
variable*

Observational variables	Loading coefficients
	1
HL1	0,875
HL2	0,858
HL3	0,770
HL4	0,767
HL5	0,766
Eigenvalue	3,272
"Total variance extracted	65,439

*Factor
(EFA)
dependent
group.*

(Source: The results of processing survey data in the SPSS software)

According to the analysis results (Table 6), the group of 4 observed variables included in the analysis converged and differentiated into 1 factor. The factor loadings of the 5 observed variables are all greater than 0.6, indicating that the group of dependent variables is consistent with the assumption of the research model. The observed variables and the factor group are retained and used for further analysis.

5.1.5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

(i) Evaluate the model fit through the adjusted R-squared coefficient.

The coefficient of determination R-squared (R^2) is used to assess the goodness-of-fit of the research model. The first step is to check the adequacy of the model.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R ²	R ² adjusted	Standard error	Durbin-Watson
1	0,787 ^a	0,619	0,608	0,46360	1,717

Tab 7: R2 (R square) coefficient

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

The adjusted R-squared coefficient is 0.608, indicating that this model explains 60.8% of the variation in the dependent variable (customer satisfaction) through the four independent variable factors. Therefore, the research model is deemed appropriate and closely related. Additionally, the result shows that the adjusted R-squared is smaller than the R-squared used to assess the model's fit, which is safer as it does not inflate the model's fit.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	50,618	4	12,654	58,879	,000 ^b
	Residual	31,164	145	,215		
	Total	81,782	149			

Tab 8: Test Anova

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

According to the results in Table 8, the F-test has a significance value (Sig.) of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected, indicating that R-squared is not equal to 0 with statistical significance. This implies that the regression model is appropriate. In other words, the model fits the overall data well, and the independent variables in the model can explain the variation in the dependent variable.

5.1.6. Research hypothesis test

The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 9.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized regression coefficients		Standardized regression coefficients	t	Sig.	Multicollinearity statistics	
		B	Standard error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0,358	0,257		1,395	0,165		
	HI	0,310	0,050	0,373	6,215	0,000	0,731	1,368
	TC	0,248	0,056	0,256	4,431	0,000	0,790	1,267

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SD	0,218	0,046	0,281	4,711	0,000	0,738	1,355
LH	0,147	0,047	0,173	3,140	0,002	0,868	1,152

a. Dependent Variable: HL

Tab 9: Result of regression analysis model

(Source: SPSS analysis results)

The accepted regression equation is as follows:

$$HL = 0,373 + 0,310*HI + 0,248TC + 0,218*SD + 0,147*LH$$

Conclusion: The results of the standardized regression coefficients analysis indicate that the independent factors have varying degrees of influence on the dependent variable. The influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable ranks in descending order as follows: usefulness > ease of use > reliability > flexibility.

5.2. Conclusion

From the research results, it is evident that customer satisfaction is influenced by various factors within the quality of the logistics information system. Specifically, the usefulness, reliability, ease of use, and flexibility of the logistics information system that customers have used positively impact their satisfaction. Therefore, to enhance customer satisfaction, service providers and commercial enterprises need to focus on improving the logistics information system.

Firstly, enhancing the usefulness of the logistics information system involves diversifying data sources, improving data analysis capabilities, and listening to user feedback. Internal data can be collected from ERP, CRM, and WMS systems, while external data can be gathered through technologies like APIs and web scraping. Advanced data analysis tools such as Machine Learning and AI should be integrated into the logistics information system. Additionally, gathering user feedback through surveys, interviews, and focus groups is crucial. After collecting feedback, businesses should analyze it and propose solutions to enhance the system.

Secondly, improving the reliability of the logistics information system can be achieved by enhancing information sharing among stakeholders and improving maintenance efficiency. When information is shared effectively and promptly among stakeholders, the system can detect and diagnose issues more quickly. With detailed information about the system's status, stakeholders can collaboratively identify and resolve

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issues efficiently, minimizing downtime and enhancing system reliability. Furthermore, enhancing the quality of maintenance work directly impacts system lifespan, performance, and the ability to improve work quality.

Thirdly, improving the ease of use of logistics information system involves ensuring that system components are logically organized and accessible to users. Clear navigation should be provided using functional buttons, directional arrows, and other user-friendly features to guide users to important sections of the interface. Constant monitoring and rectification of login errors encountered by users help them access the system easily and quickly.

Lastly, enhancing the flexibility of logistics information system requires seeking software solution providers specializing in the enterprise's strengths. To balance automation and mechanization in logistics, domestic logistics enterprises should explore logistics 4.0 applications primarily based on the Internet of Things, Big Data, Blockchain, Robotics and autonomous vehicles, Virtual and Augmented Reality technologies.

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